

ASSESSING THE NEXUS OF THE KNOWLEDGE, SKILLS, AND ATTITUDES IN EMERGENCY AND DISASTER RESPONSE AMONG NURSES

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ABSTRACT

This study determined nurses' knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response in selected hospitals in Eastern Pangasinan. It tackled their age, civil status, highest educational attainment, position, monthly family income, years in service, and a number of relevant trainings on emergency and disaster. The study utilized the descriptive research design and a survey questionnaire as the primary tools for gathering data. Several statistical tools were used: frequency and percentage, weighted mean, t-test, Scheffe test, and ANOVA (Analysis of Variance). The nurse respondents were young adults, singles, and holders of bachelor's degrees. The majority were staff nurses, earning an average monthly income, having been in the service for many years, and receiving inadequate relevant training in emergency and disaster nursing. The respondents were knowledgeable about emergency and disaster response, were skillful in attending to patients in the ER, and practiced the right attitudes in handling emergency and disaster response. Nurses who finished units leading to a master's degree claim to have better skills in emergency and disaster response than those who are already master's degree holders; the skills of the nurses in emergency and disaster response are significantly different across positions. Staff nurses are more skillful in emergency and disaster response compared to supervisors. The more relevant training the nurses have attended, the more knowledgeable they are in emergency and disaster response.

Keywords: *Knowledge, Skills, Attitudes, Emergency, Disaster*

INTRODUCTION

The role of nurses is necessary, particularly in the emergency room. They do the screenings, care for the critically ill, implement triage protocols, communicate with families, and attend to the dying. They worked in different areas since they were on a rotation schedule. They provide and learn new skills, like being safety officers and caring for severely ill patients. They make triage plans in place. They reallocate resources, and nurses lead and innovate during a crisis (Moore & Images, 2020). Nurses' commitment, flexibility, and compliance during the COVID-19 pandemic have been significant. Despite challenges, the nurses provided compassionate care to patients needing care. Nurses learn new skills, adapt to new roles, and lead innovations during a crisis. Nurses must be acknowledged for their endless support, ensuring the resources necessary to sustain the delivery of high-quality care to patients. Their unwavering dedication to patient care proves their essential role in our healthcare system. Nurses' compassion and skills must continue to be appreciated. Time is necessary for the emergency room every minute counts on saving lives and preventing the decline of a patient's condition. By efficiently triaging patients, ER nurses knew those that required immediate attention and prioritization in their care. They can ensure that critical interventions are initiated immediately, potentially preventing further complications or even death. Prioritizing patient care helps streamline the flow of patients in the emergency room, reducing waiting times and improving overall efficiency. ER nurses are trained to assess patients immediately, noting manifestations that need urgent intervention. They use their clinical judgment and knowledge to evaluate the overall condition and decide the patient's priority level. It is a delicate balancing act, as they must consider not only the understanding of the patient's condition but also the availability of resources and the needs of other patients in the emergency room.

In the fast-paced setting of an emergency room, nurses take the lead in prioritizing patient well-being by evaluating individuals to gauge the urgency of their requirements. By pinpointing those needing care, nurses ensure interventions to avert further decline or even save lives. This method improves outcomes and boosts emergency room efficiency by managing patient traffic efficiently. With their skills and unwavering commitment, ER nurses deliver top-notch care to anyone seeking assistance in the emergency ward.

Nurses have been and continue to be pivotal in safeguarding the public during and after these disasters, public health emergencies, and, most recently, the COVID-19 pandemic. In all phases of a disaster event, nurses, working with physicians and other healthcare team members, play a central role in the response. Before, during, and after disasters, nurses provide education, community engagement, and health promotion and implement interventions to safeguard public health. They provide first aid, advanced clinical care, and lifesaving medications; assess and triage victims; allocate scarce resources; and monitor ongoing physical and mental health needs. Nurses also assist with organizational logistics by developing operational response protocols and security measures and performing statistical analysis of individual- and community-level data. Basic knowledge about health system emergency preparedness is generally lacking

among nurses, including school nurses, who, as discussed above, are expected to play critical roles during public health emergencies. Gaps in education and training are evident in nursing leadership as well. The nation's nurses are unprepared for disaster and public health emergency response (ANA, 2023). Nurses are crucial in safeguarding public health during disasters, including the COVID-19 pandemic, by addressing the gaps in their education. However, there are significant gaps in their preparedness for emergency response due to a lack of education and training. Investing in their education and training is necessary to ensure they can respond effectively and protect public health. By supporting nurses, we can empower them to serve their communities better and keep us safe during times of crisis.

Professional preparation of nurses to manage disasters is critical to safe and effective rescue and response. Nurses in disaster settings must have clear leadership and rescue policies to ensure they can react to disaster situations (Li et al., 2017). Many nurses who have reported being part of disaster response teams experience psychological distress, which is exacerbated by a lack of effective management, communication mechanisms, and resources. In an era marked by significant global warming, natural disasters are becoming more prevalent, with occurrences such as earthquakes, tsunamis, volcanic activity, floods, and landslides occurring more frequently. In this context, possessing professional nursing skills in disaster response is paramount. During the more recent coronavirus (COVID-19) outbreak, nurses have been instrumental to the disaster response teams, relying on their clinical skills to adequately manage complex clinical demands in highly complex and volatile situations. All nurses must be responsive and be able to provide effective disaster relief (Li Xue et al., 2020).

Professional nursing skills in disaster response are indispensable, particularly in the face of increasing natural disasters because of global warming. Nurses play a pivotal role in disaster response teams, relying on their expertise to manage complex clinical demands in highly volatile situations, as evidenced by their crucial contributions during the COVID-19 pandemic (Hamdi, A. 2023). Given these challenges and responsibilities, all nurses must adequately prepare to deliver effective disaster relief. Underscores the critical need for ongoing training, equitable allocation of resources, and supportive systems to enable nurses to fulfil their roles effectively in disaster response efforts.

Strengthening nurses' capacity to aid in disaster preparedness and public health emergency response is fundamental to enhancing nursing's role in addressing and improving health and healthcare equity. Disaster management efforts are directed towards minimizing or preventing potential losses caused by hazards, ensuring timely and suitable assistance to those affected disaster victims, and achieving a rapid and effective recovery. Hospitals must remain safe and functional during and after disasters. Preparedness for front-line workers includes clinical skills and knowledge for providing patient care and protecting the public from becoming ill.

The increasing frequency of natural and environmental disasters and public health emergencies such as the COVID-19 pandemic highlight the critical importance of having

nursing professionals prepared with the knowledge, skills, and abilities to respond. Emergency room nurses give first aid, advanced clinical care, and lifesaving medications; assess and triage victims; allocate scarce resources; and monitor ongoing physical and mental health needs (University of Cincinnati, n.d., as cited on their website).

During the response, the most critical phase of disaster management is for nurses to activate the hospital disaster plan, triage cases, provide emergency treatment for injured people, help coordinate evacuations, and transport patients to other medical facilities. In diverse clinical settings and throughout every stage of a disaster, nurses collaborate with physicians and other healthcare team members, holding a central position in the response. Preceding, during, and following emergencies and disasters, nurses undertake tasks such as education, community engagement, health promotion, and intervention implementation to protect public health. Additionally, nurses contribute to organizational logistics by creating operational response protocols, implementing security measures, and conducting statistical analysis of patient data. The nurses activate organizational emergency operations plans, participate in incident command systems, oversee personal protective equipment (PPE) use, and provide crisis leadership and communications, often at risk to their health (Flaubert, 2021).

Their responsibilities include activating hospital disaster plans, triaging cases, providing emergency treatment, coordinating evacuations, and transporting patients to other medical facilities. Additionally, nurses engage in education, community outreach, and health promotion to safeguard public health before, during, and after emergencies. They also contribute to organizational logistics by developing response protocols, implementing security measures, and analysing patient data. Moreover, nurses assume leadership roles during crises, overseeing the use of personal protective equipment and facilitating communication, often at personal risk. It highlights the indispensable contribution of nurses in ensuring effective disaster response and underscores the importance of supporting their efforts to safeguard public health and safety.

Nurses' roles in pandemics and other infectious disease outbreaks are multifaceted and may include a) supporting and advising in epidemic surveillance and detection, such as contact tracing; b). working in point-of-distribution clinics to screen, test, and distribute vaccines and other medical countermeasures; c). employing prevention and response interventions; d) providing direct hospital-based treatment for impacted individuals; e). educating patients and the public to decrease the risk for infection; f) providing health systems and community-based leadership; and g) counseling and supporting community members to alleviate fear and anxiety (Veenema et al., 2020).

These diverse roles highlight nurses' significant contributions in responding to pandemics and infectious disease outbreaks, both in clinical settings and within communities. Nurses are multifaceted and indispensable in addressing pandemics and infectious disease outbreaks. Their involvement spans various aspects of epidemic management, including surveillance, prevention, treatment, education, and community support. In times of public health emergencies, nurses offer invaluable expertise and leadership, tirelessly working to ensure nurses diligently work to safeguard the health and

welfare of both individuals and communities during public health emergencies. Their dedication, compassion, and skills are instrumental in mitigating the spread of infectious diseases, supporting affected individuals, and alleviating fear and anxiety during times of crisis. The contributions of nurses in pandemic response underscore their invaluable role in promoting public health and ensuring the resilience of healthcare systems worldwide.

Infectious disease outbreaks have occurred more frequently and at a higher intensity over the past few decades. The healthcare system and individual front-line healthcare workers must be adequately prepared to respond to such events. Preparedness at the system level includes understanding the capacity of a hospital or health care system in advance of a potential public health emergency, including workforce capacity and capabilities and access to PPE, medical supplies, medical gases, and ventilators. It also requires organizing an action plan that includes the essential elements of managing the challenges such an event may impose on the institution. However, the preparedness of the U.S. healthcare system to manage a pediatric surge during a pandemic has been recognized as an essential improvement (Anthony et al., 2017). Recognizing the U.S. healthcare system's limitations in managing pediatric surges during pandemics highlights a critical gap. Healthcare systems must address these deficiencies promptly. This gap underscores the importance of addressing specific vulnerabilities within healthcare systems, particularly ensuring the readiness to respond effectively to pediatric populations' unique needs and challenges during infectious disease outbreaks. By recognizing and addressing these deficiencies, healthcare systems can better protect the health and well-being of all individuals, including vulnerable populations, during public health emergencies.

Nurses have experienced significant psychological and moral distress during the pandemic. Results of a survey conducted by the American Nurses Association (ANA, 2020) reveal that 87 percent of nurses were afraid to go to work, 36 percent had cared for an infectious patient without having adequate PPE, and only 11 percent felt well prepared to care for a patient with COVID-19. It also revealed intermittent shortages of PPE for nurses persisted seven months into the pandemic, particularly for those working in smaller rural hospitals, home care, and palliative care. Nurses were asked to extend and reuse N95 masks long after the CDC's recommended guidelines. Nurses working in long-term care facilities, home care, palliative care, and small rural hospitals were particularly vulnerable as caregivers in environments with high risk and high mortality (ANA, 2020).

The American Nurses Association (ANA) survey in 2020 sheds light on the immense challenges nurses face during the pandemic. Their psychological and moral distress, inadequate access to personal protective equipment (PPE), and the need to reuse N95 masks highlight the critical issues they encountered. Despite these obstacles, nurses demonstrated unwavering dedication and resilience while caring for patients in high-risk environments. Reflecting on their sacrifices, we must recognize and support their tireless efforts. The results emphasize the pressing requirement for enhanced preparedness, adequate PPE supply, and mental health support for healthcare

professionals. As we move forward, addressing these issues will be crucial to ensuring the well-being of our frontline heroes.

COVID-19 is one example of the significant burden imposed by disasters and public health emergencies on the health of populations, healthcare professionals, and nurses. The pandemic has created multiple challenges, particularly in managing its effects across diverse and highly vulnerable populations and exacerbated existing health inequities. Future natural disasters and infectious disease outbreaks will present similar, if not more significant, challenges for nursing. Bold, anticipatory action is needed to advance nurse readiness for these events (Flaubert, 2021). By addressing these challenges, proactive preparation, ongoing education, and collaboration are essential for nurses to meet the challenges posed by future emergencies. By taking bold and anticipatory action, we can enhance nurse readiness and strengthen overall public health outcomes.

The need for emergency care services is predicted to remain high, as manifested by the crowding phenomenon in emergency departments (EDs). This has impacted the decreasing quality of care and treatment, the increased adverse event rate, and the increased mortality rate in Emergency Departments. The availability of clear emergency nurses' competencies is critical for safe and effective emergency health care services. Safe and effective emergency care services can be linked to the availability of clear nurse competency. Clear competency for nurses in ED settings is needed as it describes the essential abilities to accomplish the nurses' role in an emergency (Trisyani et al., 2019). By establishing clear competency standards, healthcare organizations can ensure that their emergency nurses are adequately prepared to handle the challenges they may encounter in the ED, including clinical skills, communication, critical thinking, and decision-making abilities, all of which are essential for delivering safe and effective care to patients in emergency settings. Ultimately, having clear nurse competencies in the ED improves patient outcomes and enhances the overall quality of emergency care services. Well-defined nurse competencies empower emergency nurses to provide high-quality care, even in challenging situations.

There are still gaps in disaster preparedness and core competencies for emergency nurses that must be addressed. Nursing managers must support an improvement in nursing disaster core competencies. This may be done by conducting sessions for routine disaster scenarios and providing formal disaster preparedness training. Analysis results indicated that nursing disaster core competencies were perceived better by older nurses who had experience in the disaster stage and nurses with disaster response experience and lower professional experience. Nurses with a post-diploma degree and bachelor's degree were perceived to have lower disaster core competency than nurses with a master's or Ph.D. degree (Chegini et al., 2020). Nursing managers should prioritize supporting the improvement of disaster core competencies among their teams through training initiatives and hands-on experience. By addressing these gaps and ensuring that nurses are adequately prepared, healthcare organizations

can enhance their resilience, and we can better serve our communities during emergencies.

The study of Naser et al. (2018) on the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of Yemeni professionals found that they needed more preparedness for emergencies and disasters. The respondents needed to exhibit better knowledge. The educational level was a critical factor in the knowledge gap among respondents. Regardless of the period of experience, postgraduate staff were more knowledgeable than graduates. Most study respondents showed a positive attitude level toward emergency and disaster preparedness.

Labrague et al. (2018) found that factors that increase preparedness for disaster response include previous disaster response experience and disaster-related training. Nurses need to be more prepared and feel confident responding effectively to disasters. Despite growing initiatives to prepare nurses for any disasters, evidence suggests they need to prepare for disaster response.

The study conducted by McNeill et al. 2020 on nurses' preparedness during disasters indicates significant weaknesses in nurses' professional emergency preparedness competence. Positive correlations exist between the likelihood to report, personal preparedness, and professional emergency preparedness competence. Nurses across the United States need more competence in professional emergency preparedness.

Al Harti et al. (2020) found in their study that nurses need to be prepared to respond immediately to reduce the impact of disasters. However, nurses face several challenges in all phases of disaster management. Significant barriers facing nurses include the following: inadequate level of preparedness, poor formal education, lack of research, ethical and legal issues, and issues related to nurses' roles in disasters. Educators, researchers, and stakeholders must tackle these issues and improve disaster nursing.

The National Library of (Medicine, 2019) found that the nation's nurses must prepare for disaster and public health emergency response. A bold and expansive effort, executed across multiple platforms, will be needed to fully support nurses preparing for disaster and public health emergency response. It is essential to convene experts who can develop a national strategic plan articulating the existing deficiencies and safeguards taken. Rapid action is needed across nursing education, practice, policy, and research to address the gaps in nursing's disaster preparedness and improve its capacity to advocate for population health and health equity during such events. Underscore the need for immediate and concerted efforts to bolster nurses' preparedness for disaster and public health emergency response. Addressing these challenges is essential for strengthening the resilience of the healthcare system and ensuring the well-being of communities in times of crisis.

Hospitals and their Emergency Departments (ED) are at risk for crises and their potential escalation to hospital disasters. Emerging risks due to climate-related

emergencies, infectious disease outbreaks, terrorism, and cyber-attacks pose threats. If a hospital is not ready, it undermines the capacity of administration and staff to safeguard the safety of patients. Therefore, hospitals and their EDs must check and enhance their preparedness for these contingencies (Barten et al., 2021). Hospitals and their Emergency Departments (EDs) must regularly evaluate and, if needed, improve their preparedness for such contingencies. It involves establishing comprehensive emergency response plans, ensuring ample availability of resources and supplies, conducting regular training exercises, and establishing efficient internal and external communication channels. By prioritizing preparedness measures, hospitals can mitigate the impact of potential crises or disasters and ensure their patients' safety and continuous care. Collaborating with local authorities, healthcare partners, and community organizations is essential in building a resilient healthcare system that addresses diverse emergencies and hazards.

Their study on the challenges nurses encounter in the emergency room identified several significant challenges confronting nurses working in the emergency unit: managerial processes and inadequate managerial support. These challenges need to be addressed to promote quality emergency nursing care. Hospital management should validate and address the concerns of the Emergency Department nurses (Afaya et al., 2021). The research on the challenges nurses face in the emergency room highlighted several significant obstacles that nurses encounter in this setting, particularly those associated with managerial processes and a lack of sufficient managerial support. These challenges are critical to address to enhance the quality of emergency nursing care. Hospital management must acknowledge and tackle the concerns nurses in the Emergency Department raise. By doing so, management can empower nurses to provide better patient care and improve the general outcomes in the emergency room setting.

The researcher conducted the study since he was assigned to the emergency room. He wants to determine nurses' knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergencies and disasters, just like what transpired in the past years regarding the incidence of emergency conditions during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Theoretical/ Conceptual Framework

The study adopted the Emergency management theory. This theory studies how to prevent, prepare, respond, and recover from disasters and emergencies. It draws on various disciplines to understand complex and uncertain situations' causes, effects, and solutions. The study adopted the theory because it focused on emergencies, which are nurses' knowledge, skills, and attitudes during emergencies and disasters.

It also utilized the Virginia Henderson theory on nursing needs, which conceptualized the nurse's role as assisting sick or healthy individuals to gain independence in meeting 14 fundamental needs.

The theory suggests that individuals have fundamental needs integral to their health, and they may require assistance to attain health and independence or experience a peaceful death. Nurses apply this theory in the emergency room setting as they provide support and care to needy patients.

The study assessed the nexus of the knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response among emergency room nurses in government hospitals in Eastern Pangasinan. Box number 1 is the input that deals with the profile of the respondents and the nexus of the knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response among emergency room nurses. Box number 2 is the process that deals with data gathering, interpretation, and analysis. Box number 3 is the Output focusing on the proposed training program to improve emergency room nurses' knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study determined the nexus of the knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response among emergency room nurses in government hospitals in Eastern Pangasinan.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of their;
 - a. age;
 - b. civil status;
 - c. highest educational attainment;
 - d. monthly family income;
 - e. position;
 - f. number of years in service; and
 - g. relevant trainings attended in emergency and disaster nursing for the past five years?
2. What are the nexus in emergency and disaster response among the emergency room nurses along;
 - a. knowledge;
 - b. skills; and,
 - c. attitude?
3. Is there a significant difference between the nexus of knowledge, skills, and attitudes of the respondents on emergency and disaster response across their profile variables?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the nexus of the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of the respondents on emergency and disaster response across their profile variables?
5. Based on the findings, what proposed training program can be formulated to improve the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of the respondents in emergency and disaster the response among ER nurses?

Null Hypothesis

The study was tested in its null form at a 0.05 level of significance;

1. There is no significant relationship between the nexus of the respondents' knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response across their profile variables.
2. The nexus of the respondents' knowledge, skills, and attitudes on emergency and disaster response across their profile variables is the same.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter explains the research methodology, which includes discussions on the research design, study participants, sampling strategy, data collection instruments, data collection procedures, statistical data treatment, and tools employed for data analysis.

Research Design

The study employed descriptive research methodology using the questionnaire as a data-gathering tool to determine the nexus of the respondents' knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response in the emergency room. According to Calderon (2018) descriptive research is a purposive process of gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about prevailing conditions, practices, beliefs, processes, trends, and cause effect relationships and the making adequate and accurate interpretation about such data with or without the aid of statistical methods. Descriptive research this type of research describes what exists and may help to uncover new facts and meaning. The purpose of descriptive research is to observe, describe and document aspects of situation as it naturally occurs. This involves the collection of data that will provide an account or description of individuals, groups, or situation.

Population and Locale of the Study

The study's respondents were 50 emergency room nurses employed in 5 selected hospitals in Eastern Pangasinan. Purposive sampling was used to represent the population, and the sample was delimited to those nurses assigned to the emergency room. The study was conducted during the second semester of 2023-2024.

Data Gathering Tool

The study utilized a survey questionnaire based on previous studies and articles related to the study. Part I focused on the respondents' profiles regarding their age and civil status, highest educational attainment, monthly family income, position, number of years in service, and relevant seminars on emergencies and disasters for the past five years. Part II tackled the nexus of the knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response among ER nurses.

Validation of Instrument

The questionnaire was employed to collect data from the respondents. The questionnaire items were derived from various articles and research studies concerning knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response among emergency room nurses. However, it underwent validation by experts in emergency nursing, including a faculty researcher, an instructor specializing in emergency and disaster

nursing, and emergency room nurses. The combined rating indicated a high level of validity.

Data Gathering Procedures

Before gathering data, the researcher secured permission from the Dean of the Institute of Graduate and Advanced Studies to conduct the study. When permission was granted from the Institute of Graduate and Advanced Studies, the researcher requested and coordinated with the Chief of Hospitals through the Chief Nurses for permission to conduct the study. After securing the permission, the researcher secured consent from the respondents. Data was gathered personally by the researcher in the Second semester of 2023-2024.

Treatment of Data

Frequency and percentage were used for Problem No.1 on the respondent's profile.

The frequency was determined based on the number of respondents who answered or checked a particular item on the questionnaire.

$$\text{Formula: } P = \frac{F \times 100}{N}$$

where: P = percentage

F = frequency

N = total number of respondents

Problem No. 2 on the nexus of the knowledge, skills, and attitudes on emergency and disaster response among emergency room nurses weighted mean using the five-point Likert scale.

Literal Value	Statistical Limit	Descriptive Equivalent	Transmuted Rating
A	4.50 – 5.00	Always	Highly Knowledgeable
B	3.50 – 4.49	Often	Knowledgeable
C	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes	Moderately Knowledgeable
D	1.50 – 2.49	Seldom	Slightly Knowledgeable
E	1.00 – 1.49	Never	Not Knowledgeable

For the nexus of emergency and disaster response skills among emergency room nurses, a weighted mean was used using the five-point Likert scale.

Literal Value	Statistical Value	Descriptive Equivalent	Transmuted Rating
A	4.50 – 5.00	Always	Highly Skillful
B	3.50 – 4.49	Often	Skillful
C	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes	Moderately Skillful
D	1.50 – 2.49	Seldom	Slightly Skillful
E	1.00 – 1.49	Never	Not Skillful

For the nexus of emergency room nurse practices on emergency and disaster response, the weighted mean was used using the five-point Likert scale.

Literal Value	Statistical Value	Descriptive Equivalent
A	4.50 – 5.00	Always
B	3.50 – 4.49	Often
C	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes
D	1.50 – 2.49	Seldom
E	1.00 – 1.49	Never

The weighted mean is the mean of a set of values wherein each value or measurement has a different weight or degree of importance.

Formula: $\bar{x} = \frac{\sum fi}{N}$

where: "x̄" = weighted mean

N = total # of population; and

fi = frequencies corresponding to the given items.

For Problems Nos. 3 and 4, on the significant relationships and differences between the nexus of the respondents' knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response, Analysis of Variance was used to test the difference. In contrast, Chi-Square was used to test the relationship between variables.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

$$F = \frac{MSb}{MSw}$$

Where:

MSb - Mean Square Between

MSw - Mean Square Within

Chi-Square

$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

Where: O =observed number of cases

$$E = \frac{(\text{row total}) (\text{column total})}{\text{Grand total}}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Part 1. Respondent's Profile

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, civil status, highest educational attainment, position, monthly family income, number of years in service, and number of relevant trainings on emergency and disaster.

Age. It can be gleaned from the table that most respondents are in the age bracket of 31-40 years old, with a frequency of 34, or 68 percent, followed by 21-30 and 41-50, with a frequency of 8, or 16 percent. It revealed that the respondents were young adults. The data presented indicates a significant concentration of respondents within the 31-40 age bracket; this shows a substantial concentration of respondents in this age group, which aligns with Erikson's psychosocial stages of development. Erikson emphasizes the importance of forming personal connections. Establishing intimate relationships is considered a marker of success in this developmental phase; according to Erikson, 31-40-year-olds are considered young adults and emphasize the importance of forming personal connections. Young adults need to create intimate, loving relationships with other people. Success leads to strong relationships, while failure results in loneliness and isolation. This stage covers the period of early adulthood when people are exploring personal relationships. (McLeod 2024). The concentration of respondents within the 31-40 age bracket underscores the importance of considering developmental stages and psychosocial factors when analyzing workforce dynamics and designing interventions to promote professional fulfillment and quality patient care.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents in Terms of their Profile Variables
n=50

Profile Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age (in years)		
21 – 30	8	16.0
31 – 40	34	68.0
41 – 50	8	16.0
Civil Status		
Single	32	64.0
Married	18	36.0
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	30	60.0
With Master's units	17	34.0
Master's Degree	3	6.0
Position		
Staff Nurse	45	90.0
Supervisor	2	4.0
Head Nurse	3	6.0
Monthly Family Income (in Php)		
Below P15,000	7	14.0
15,001-25,000	30	60.0
35,001-45,000	13	26.0
Number of Years in Service		
Below 1 year	6	12.0
1 – 2	8	16.0
3 – 4	9	18.0
5 and above	27	54.0
Number of Relevant Trainings on Emergency and Disaster		
1 – 2	34	68.0
3 – 4	8	16.0
5 and above	8	16.0

Civil status. Most respondents were single, with a frequency of 32, or 64 percent, followed by married, with a frequency of 18, or 36 percent. It revealed that the respondents were not into marital relationships and were pursuing their experiences in

their field of assignment. Being single gives you a unique opportunity to discover yourself deeply. It underscores the positive aspects of being single, suggesting it can lead to a more optimistic outlook. This perspective is valuable, especially in a society that prioritizes marital relationships. It is essential to recognize that being single is not just a status but an opportunity for self-discovery and setting one's path. You can shape a life that reflects your unique priorities and then seek companionship to share it with. According to Shockley and Allen (2012), employees with a spouse and/or children typically have more life duties compared to their single counterparts. However, it is essential to recognize that every individual's circumstances vary, and there are numerous factors beyond marital status and parenthood that can impact an employee's workload and life responsibilities.

Highest educational attainment. It revealed that most respondents were bachelor's degree holders, with a frequency of 30 or 60 percent, followed by those with master units, with a frequency of 17 or 34 percent, and MAN degree, with a frequency of 3 or 6 percent. It showed that many respondents needed to pursue a higher level of learning. This trend could be attributed to the lack of competitiveness in their salaries, resulting in nurses opting out of pursuing master's or doctoral programs, so some nurses fail to enroll in the master's or doctoral program. Notably, most hold a bachelor's degree, which suggests a solid foundation of professional education. As per the Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE), an entry-level registered nurse receives an average monthly salary of P8,000 to P13,500. Registered nurses hired by hospitals commonly receive an average wage of P9,757 a month. Despite this, the financial challenges may persist, affecting nurses' decisions to pursue further education. Healthcare workers' occupations inherently expose them to the risk of contracting various diseases, including the lethal COVID-19. Despite receiving low wages, nurses stay in the profession to help save lives (Magsambol, 2020). This data highlights the importance of addressing financial barriers to higher education for nurses and recognizing their dedication to providing quality care despite their challenges.

Position. It is definable that most respondents were ER staff nurses, with a frequency of 45 or 90 percent, Head nurses, with a frequency of 3 or 6 percent, and Nurse Supervisors, with a frequency of 2 or 4 percent. It indicates more rank-and-file staff nurses than supervisors, consistent with the usual arrangement in many healthcare settings. In these settings, most nursing workforce consists of staff nurses directly engaged in patient care duties. Their role is vital as they are often the first point of contact for patients, and they have a significant role in assessing and monitoring their condition and providing the necessary care and support for recovery. According to Peters (2021), a staff nurse is a registered nurse who provides high-quality care to patients at the bedside, residents of nursing homes, or in a hospital. They are responsible for initial patient assessment, monitoring patients' vital signs, and nurturing patients to recovery.

Monthly family income. It showed that most respondents received an income of P15,001-P25,000, with a frequency of 30, or 60 per cent, P35,001-P45,000, with a frequency of 13, or 26 per cent, P20,001-30,000 and below P15,000, with a frequency of 7, or 14 per cent. It revealed that the respondents received an average monthly income

and suggested that while earning an average income, meeting the necessary living standards may still be challenging, especially considering the cost of living and inflation rates. Pernia, a socio-economic planning secretary of NEDA, says a family of four needs a decent monthly income of P42,000 to live above the poverty line (Castillo, 2018). The data underscores the importance of addressing income disparities and ensuring that healthcare professionals, including nurses, receive fair compensation for their essential work. It is crucial for their well-being and sustaining a healthy and productive workforce in the healthcare sector.

Number of years in service. It can be gleaned that most of the respondents were in the service for five years and above, with a frequency of 27, or 54 per cent, 3-4, with a frequency of 9, or 18 per cent, 1-2, with a frequency of 8, or 16 per cent, and below one year, with a frequency of 6, or 12 per cent. It reflects that the respondents were in the service longer as staff nurses. Length of service is essential in the workplace because it can influence job satisfaction, work performance, and employee retention. The data underscores the importance of recognizing and valuing the experience and dedication of nurses who have served for extended periods. Supporting and retaining experienced staff nurses can contribute to a more stable and effective healthcare workforce, ultimately benefiting patient care outcomes. According to Faster Capital (n.d.), the concept of employee loyalty has been an essential part of the employer-employee relationship for a long time. It is a two-way street where employees who are loyal to their companies tend to stay longer, work harder, and promote organizational culture. Extensive tenure within a workplace not only fosters job security but also cultivates a profound sense of loyalty between employees and employers. Furthermore, it correlates with the accumulation of invaluable experience and expertise, leading to enhanced work performance and heightened quality of care delivered by nurses. These findings underscore the significance of acknowledging and appreciating the dedication and experience of long-serving nurses. By nurturing and retaining seasoned staff members, healthcare facilities can bolster the stability and efficacy of their workforce, thereby positively impacting patient care outcomes.

Relevant training on emergency and disaster. Most respondents had undergone training 1-2 times, with a frequency of 34, or 68 per cent, 3-4, and 5 and above, with a frequency of 8, or 16 per cent. This revealed that the respondents needed adequate training in emergency and disaster. The findings are like those of the National Library of Medicine (2019), where the nurses were unprepared for disasters and public health emergency responses. Nurses must be well-prepared for emergencies, as they are often on the front lines of response. Improving nurses' readiness for disaster response enhances their capacity to aid in emergencies, addresses social determinants of health, and improves healthcare equity.

Part II. Nexus of the Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes in Emergency and Disaster Response Among Nurses

Table 2 - 4 presents the nexus of the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of emergency and disaster response among nurses.

Table 2
Knowledge in Emergency and Disaster Response Among Nurses
n=50

Indicators	WM	TR
1. I know the advanced equipment to monitor and treat patients.	4.42	K
2. I prioritize care based on the patient's needs.	4.80	HK
3. I provide urgent assistance by delivering the crash cart, giving CPR, using defibrillators, ventilating the patient, and administering IV fluids.	4.64	HK
4. I assist the doctors with diagnostic procedures and tests.	4.60	HK
5. I transfer patients from the ER when they are in stable condition.	4.64	HK
6. I treat patients with life-threatening overdoses or severe trauma from accidents or violence.	4.32	K
7. I assess patients' conditions, determine the next steps for treatment, and coordinate with other team members, patients, and family members.	4.62	HK
8. I evaluate patients, offer emergency support such as first aid and cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR), and work with law enforcement to confirm the facts of the event.	4.48	K
9. I perform evaluations, determine the risk level, prioritize high-risk patients, and work with other care providers to initiate treatment and care.	4.60	HK
10. I provide urgent care, such as medication administration and intravenous (IV) fluids, communicate with parents, and treat patients and their families compassionately to manage their situations' emotional burdens.	4.66	HK
AWM	4.58	HK

Legend:

Statistical Value	Transmuted Rating (TR)
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Knowledgeable (HK)
3.50 – 4.49	Knowledgeable (K)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Knowledgeable (MK)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Knowledgeable (SK)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Knowledgeable (NK)

As gleaned from the table, the highest indicators are "I prioritize care based on the patient needs" and "provide urgent care, such as medication administration and

intravenous (IV) fluids, communicate with parents, and treat patients and their families with compassion to manage the emotional burdens of their situations," with a weighted mean of 4.66 and 4.80, or "Highly Knowledgeable." It reflects that the respondents practiced prioritization in giving their care to patients, especially in the ER, where it is the first step the patients take during admissions. When assigned to the ER, the nurses knew what they did and the patient's needs. According to Pavedahl et al. (2022), ER nurses must structure their work based on the prevailing conditions to meet patients' fundamental care needs. The organizational structure clearly states that fundamental care should be performed in the emergency room, and the registered nurses' approach to meeting patients' primary care needs is adapted to provide patients with person-centered care.

The lowest indicators are "I am aware of the advanced equipment to monitor and treat patients" and "I treat patients with life-threatening overdoses or severe trauma from accidents or violence," with a weighted mean of 4.32 and 4.42, or "Knowledgeable." It showed that the ER nurses are aware of the operation of equipment used in life-threatening and critical conditions. The indicators reflect an excellent awareness among ER nurses regarding operating advanced equipment for monitoring and treating patients in crucial situations. Nowadays, hospitals are up to date with new technologies and gadgets used in patient care, and the nurses are trained on this equipment before using it with patients. Several technological innovations have been introduced in healthcare over the years, and their implementation has proved crucial in addressing the challenges of modern health. Nurses have been called upon to become familiar with technological innovations that pervade every aspect of their profession, changing their working schedules, habits, and daily actions (Barchielli et al., 2021). There are areas for improvement in ER nurses' awareness of advanced equipment and their confidence in treating critical conditions, but the overall level of knowledge remains commendable. Continued emphasis on training and integrating technological innovations into nursing practice will further enhance patient care outcomes and strengthen the role of nurses in modern healthcare delivery.

Overall, nurses' emergency and disaster response knowledge got an average weighted mean of 4.58, or "Highly Knowledgeable." It connotes that the ER nurses are trained to give the necessary care to respond during emergencies. It suggests that ER nurses possess a high level of expertise and are well-prepared to handle emergencies, which is critical for effective patient care in high-stress situations. They are familiar with the policies and procedures in the ER. Nurses must have different competencies in responding to emergencies and during disasters. As mentioned, the Core Competency Standards of the Board of Nursing emphasize the importance of having a well-defined skill set to ensure nurses are equipped to respond to various clinical scenarios, including emergencies and disasters. These competencies cover a broad range of skills, from clinical knowledge to communication and leadership abilities, all of which contribute to the overall effectiveness of the emergency response and every nurse must adopt the competencies.

Additionally, it presents the skills in emergency and disaster response among ER nurses. As gleaned from the table, the highest indicators are “I immediately assess and triage victims needing emergency care,” “I provide emergency treatment for injured people and other victims of disasters,” and “I render first aid and advanced clinical care to patients rushed to the emergency room” with a weighted mean of 4.62 and 4.70, or “Highly Skillful.” It reflects that the nurses do an immediate assessment of their patients. Triage in the emergency room is a critical process that helps medical professionals prioritize patients based on the urgency of their conditions. It ensures that those who need immediate attention receive it promptly, which can be lifesaving in critical situations. According to Yancey and O’Rourke (2023), triage is utilized in the emergency room to categorize patients based on the severity of their injuries and, by extension, the order in which multiple patients require immediate care and monitoring.

Table 3
Skills in Emergency and Disaster Response Among Nurses
n=50

Indicators	WM	TR
1. I immediately assess and triage victims needing emergency care.	4.70	HS
2. I allocate scarce resources and make sure immediate care is provided.	4.54	HS
3. I provide emergency treatment for injured people and other victims of disasters.	4.62	HS
4. I coordinate evacuations and the transfer of patients to other medical facilities.	4.40	S
5. I assure prompt and appropriate assistance to the victims of a disaster or any emergencies.	4.42	S
6. I monitor emergency patients and their immediate family members' ongoing physical and mental health needs.	4.44	S
7. I render first aid and advanced clinical care to patients who are rushed to the emergency room.	4.62	HS
8. I abide by organizational logistics by developing operational response protocols and security measures.	4.44	S
9. I use personal protective equipment (PPE) to prevent possible exposure to body discharges and fluids of patients in the emergency room.	4.52	HS
10. I employ prevention and response interventions for all victims of emergencies and disasters.	4.48	S
	AWM	HS
	4.52	HS

Legend:

Statistical Limit	Transmuted Rating (TR)
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Skillful (HS)
3.50 – 4.49	Skillful (S)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Skillful (MS)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Skillful (SS)

The indicators with the lowest scores are "I coordinate evacuations and the transfer of patients to other medical facilities" and "I ensure that victims of disasters or any emergencies receive prompt and appropriate assistance," both rated as "Skillful" with a weighted mean of 4.40 and 4.42, respectively. It showed that the ER nurses have the skills to properly evacuate and transfer patients to more prominent hospitals. According to Melnychuk et al. (2022), hospitals are a vital component of disaster response but are susceptible to the effects of disasters, including infrastructure damage that disrupts patient care. When hospitals are directly affected by a disaster, these events offer an opportunity for evacuation and transfer, evaluation, and improvement of preparedness and response efforts.

Overall, the skills in emergency and disaster response among nurses got an average weighted mean of 4.52, or "Highly Skillful." It connotes that the ER nurses knew the different procedures used in the emergency room to respond to disasters and other critical conditions. It contradicts the findings of Labrague et al. (2018) that nurses need to be prepared to answer during disasters. Nevertheless, while the findings are promising, continuous efforts should be made to enhance nurses' preparedness and skills in disaster response. Ongoing training, regular drills, and collaboration with other emergency responders can help nurses remain adept at managing critical situations and providing optimal patient care during emergencies and disasters. Continuous improvement in nurses' preparedness and skills in disaster response is vital to ensure effective patient care during emergencies and disasters. Although the current results show promise, continuing sustained efforts in this area. Regular training sessions, drills, and collaboration with other emergency responders can significantly enhance nurses' readiness to manage critical situations. Through continuous skill enhancement and adherence to best practices, nurses can substantially contribute to alleviating the repercussions of disasters on public health and safety.

Table 4 presents the attitudes in emergency and disaster response among nurses.

4

**Attitudes in Emergency and Disaster Response among Nurses
n=50**

Indicators	WM	DE
1. I practice teamwork as a positive and effective construct in the emergency room.	4.82	A
2. I build a resilient team with strong leadership and communication skills, which are essential to withstand the challenging demands of the emergency room.	4.60	A
3. I observe professionalism in the context of the behaviors and actions displayed during an episode of care delivery.	4.74	A

4. I contribute knowledge, practice changes, or other aspects of health care to benefit those who receive nursing care in the emergency room.	4.68	A
5. I focus on the changing healthcare system in the emergency room, establish goals, and meet the challenges to accomplish care for emergency and disaster victims.	4.54	A
6. I consider lifelong learning as an essential component of nursing practice, particularly in the emergency room	4.70	A
7. I stimulate professional growth and foster a vibrant practice environment in the emergency room.	4.62	A
8. I strive to engage in emergency room practice with an open, inquiring mind that formulates and pursues answers to clinical and operational questions.	4.74	A
9. I perform nursing actions primarily based on doctors' orders	4.66	A
10. I contribute to the profession through ongoing self-development, accountability, mentoring, advocacy, and involvement in the emergency room.	4.72	A
	4.68	A

Legend:

Statistical Limit	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
4.50 – 5.00	Always (A)
3.50 – 4.49	Often (O)
2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes (So)
1.50 – 2.49	Seldom (S)
1.00 – 1.49	Never (N)

As gleaned from the table, all the indicators were rated with a descriptive equivalent of "Always," however the highest indicators are item numbers 1, 3, and 8, "I practice teamwork as a positive and effective construct in the emergency room," "I observe professionalism in the context of the behaviors and actions displayed during an episode of care delivery," and "I strive to engage in emergency room practice with an open, inquiring mind that formulates questions and pursues answers to clinical and operational questions," with a weighted mean of 4.82 and 4.74, and a descriptive equivalent of "Highly Always." It reflects that ER nurses observe teamwork with other health team members. Nurses need clear and effective communication with patients, their relatives, and the medical team to ensure everyone is on the same page about the patient's health status and requirements.

The lowest indicator is item 5, "I focus on the changing health care system in the emergency room, establish goals, and meet the challenges to accomplish care to emergency and disaster victims," with a weighted mean of 4.54 and a descriptive equivalent of "Always." its shows that ER nurses encounter challenges, but this does not hinder them from performing their tasks to save lives.

Overall, nurses' attitudes toward emergency and disaster response got an average weighted mean of 4.68 and a descriptive equivalent of "Always." it indicates that the ER nurses showed the proper attitudes toward responding to emergencies and disasters. Situations can evolve rapidly in the emergency room, necessitating that ER nurses adapt to these changes and make prompt decisions to deliver the best possible care to their patients.

Moreover, it presents the knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response among nurses.

Summary of the Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes in Emergency and Disaster Response Among Nurses

As gleaned from the table, the indicators were rated "Highly Practiced," "Highly Skillful," and "Always." Still, the highest aspect is attitude, with a weighted mean of 4.68 and a descriptive equivalent of "Always." It is followed by "Knowledge," with a weighted mean of 4.58, or "Highly Knowledgeable." The emergency room is a high-pressure environment that comes with its own set of challenges. Emergency room (ER) nurses must be able to make rapid decisions, often with limited information and under stressful conditions. They must be able to prioritize effectively, balancing the needs of multiple patients simultaneously.

Table 5
Summary of the Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes in
Emergency and Disaster Response Among Nurses
n=50

Aspect	WM	TR
Knowledge	4.58	HK
Skills	4.52	HS
Attitude	4.68	A

Legend:

Statistical Range	Transmuted Rating
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Knowledgeable (HK)/Highly Skillful (HS)/ Always (A)
3.50 – 4.49	Knowledgeable (K) / Skillful (S) / Often (O)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Knowledgeable (MK) / Moderately Skillful (MS) / Sometimes (So)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Knowledgeable (SK) / Slightly Skillful (SS) /Seldom (S)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Knowledgeable (NK) / Not Skillful (NS) / Never (N)

The lowest aspect is on "Skills," with a weighted mean of 4.52, or "Highly Skillful." It revealed that the ER nurses had the skills to attend to emergencies and disaster responses. ER nurses receive training to quickly assess patients upon arrival, gather vital information, and identify any signs or symptoms that require immediate attention.

Overall, nurses' attitudes in emergency and disaster response got an average weighted mean of 4.68 and a descriptive equivalent of "Always." It connotes that the ER nurses knew the skills and attitudes needed to handle patients brought to the ER. According to Labrague et al. (2016), 80% of Filipino nurses suggested needing more time to respond to disasters. It contradicts the findings that the ER nurses were knowledgeable in handling emergencies and disasters.

Part III. Results Stressing the Difference in the Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes in Emergency and Disaster Response Among Nurses

Table 6 -14 presents the differences in the knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response among nurses.

Table 6
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes in Emergency and Disaster Response Among Nurses Across Age

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Knowledge	Between Groups	.706	2	.353	2.661	.080	Not Significant
	Within Groups	6.239	47	.133			
	Total	6.946	49				
Skills	Between Groups	.598	2	.299	1.397	.257	Not Significant
	Within Groups	10.056	47	.214			
	Total	10.654	49				
Attitudes	Between Groups	.583	2	.291	2.028	.143	Not Significant
	Within Groups	6.751	47	.144			
	Total	7.334	49				

The computed F-values show no significant difference in the nurses' knowledge, skills, and attitudes when grouped according to age. This means that age does not affect nurses' knowledge, skills, and attitudes regarding emergency and disaster response. It implies that ER nurses have comparative knowledge, skills, and attitudes when dealing with emergencies and disasters, regardless of age. It is related to the study of Nofal et al. (2018), which found that nurses below 30 years old level of knowledge were satisfactory with a neutral level of attitude, practice, and familiarity regarding disaster preparedness. This finding implies that ER nurses exhibit comparable levels of knowledge, skills, and attitudes regardless of their age. It highlights the consistency in preparedness and capabilities among nurses in managing emergencies and disasters, irrespective of their age group. It underscores the effectiveness of training programs and ongoing professional development initiatives to ensure nurses possess the necessary competencies to respond effectively to emergencies across all age demographics.

Table 7 shows the difference in the knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response among nurses across civil status. The computed t-values generated significance values higher than the set .05 significance level.

Table 7
t-Test Results on the Difference in the Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes in
Emergency and Disaster Response Among Nurses Across Civil Status

Aspect	Civil Status	N	Mean	Mean Difference	Standard Error Difference	df	t-value	Sig	Remarks
Knowledge	Single	32	4.54	-.113	.111	48	-	1.014	.315
	Married	18	4.65						
Skills	Single	32	4.42	-.267	.133	48	-	2.002	.051
	Married	18	4.69						
Attitudes	Single	32	4.67	-.045	.115	48	-	.396	.694
	Married	18	4.71						

This suggests acceptance of the null hypothesis; hence, there is no significant difference in the knowledge and skills of nurses in emergency and disaster response when grouped according to civil status. Single and married nurses share the same knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response, which implies that factors other than civil status may be more influential in shaping nurses' preparedness and abilities to respond to emergencies. Understanding these factors can help healthcare institutions develop targeted training programs and support systems to enhance emergency response capabilities across all groups of nurses, ultimately improving patient outcomes and overall disaster preparedness.

Table 8 displays the test results of differences in the knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response among nurses across the highest educational attainment.

Table 8
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes in
Emergency and Disaster Response Among Nurses Across Highest Educational
Attainment

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Knowledge	Between Groups	.442	2	.221	1.596	.213	Not Significant
	Within Groups	6.504	47	.138			
	Total	6.946	49				
Skills	Between Groups	1.648	2	.824	4.301	.019	Significant
	Within Groups	9.005	47	.192			
			335				

	Total	10.654	49				
Attitudes	Between Groups	.375	2	.187			
	Within Groups	6.959	47	.148	1.265	.292	Not Significant
	Total	7.334	49				

The computed F- values, along with knowledge and attitudes, generated significance values higher than the set .05 level of significance, suggestive of acceptance of the null hypothesis. Therefore, there exists no significant difference in the knowledge and attitudes of the nurses when grouped according to educational attainment.

However, a significantly lower value than .05 is evident under the computed F-value corresponding to skills. It means that the highest educational attainment of nurses affects their skills in emergency and disaster response. Table 8 presents the outcomes of the Scheffe test, which aims to pinpoint specific groups exhibiting notable skill-level disparities. Nurses possess skillful expertise in responding effectively to emergencies and managing situations during disasters. Sibandz and Scafide (2018) discovered that registered nurses with a bachelor's degree in nursing (BSN) or higher tend to possess superior skills and demonstrate a more vital application of professional values than nurses with lower academic qualifications or non-academic educational backgrounds. Furthermore, nurses with higher levels of education tend to prioritize professional values as essential components of high-quality nursing care practice.

Table 9 reveals the groups that significantly differ in skills in emergency and disaster response across the highest educational attainment.

Table 9
Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Skills in Emergency and Disaster Response among Nurses Across Highest Educational Attainment

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
Skills	w/ Master's Units vs Master's Degree Holder	.798	.020

The significant positive mean difference between nurses who earned Master's units and nurses who are master's degree holders indicates that the former has higher statistical means. It implies that nurses who finished units leading to master's degrees claim to have better skills in emergency and disaster response than those who are already master's degree holders. The study's findings contradict the study of Naser et al. (2018), which found that postgraduate staff were more knowledgeable than graduates. These findings underscore the complexity of assessing skills and knowledge in emergency and disaster response among nursing professionals and highlight the need for continued research to understand better the factors influencing perceived competency levels in this critical area of healthcare.

Table 10 displays the difference in the knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response among nurses across positions.

Table 10
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes in
Emergency and Disaster Response Among Nurses Across Position

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Knowledge	Between Groups	.398	2	.199	1.427	.250	Not Significant
	Within Groups	6.548	47	.139			
	Total	6.946	49				
Skills	Between Groups	1.766	2	.883	4.669	.014	Significant
	Within Groups	8.888	47	.189			
	Total	10.654	49				
Attitudes	Between Groups	.384	2	.192	1.300	.282	Not Significant
	Within Groups	6.949	47	.148			
	Total	7.334	49				

The computed F-values under knowledge and attitudes provided significance values higher than the set .05 significance level, which implies that no significant difference exists in the nurses' emergency and disaster response when grouped according to the position. On the other hand, nurses' emergency and disaster response skills are significantly different across positions, implying differences in their abilities. Some nurses held supervisory positions that focused more on monitoring the ER nurses. They are also knowledgeable but concentrate on direct patient care. Pavlou (2023) cited the ability to provide clinical supervision as an essential skill for any nursing supervisor. This skill is needed to ensure nurses provide safe and effective patient care. Clinical supervision also allows supervisors to identify areas where nurses may require additional training or support.

Table 11 shows the significant difference in emergency and disaster response skills among nurses across positions. A positive mean difference of .960 exists between staff nurse and supervisor groups.

Table 11
Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Skill in Emergency and Disaster Response Among Nurses Across Position

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
Skills	Staff Nurse vs Supervisor	.960	.314

It indicates that the mean values for staff nurses regarding emergency and disaster response skills are significantly higher than those of the supervisor. Staff nurses are more skillful in emergency and disaster response compared to supervisors. Supervisors usually supervise and monitor their ER nurses, not direct patient care. The emergency room (ER) nurses underwent training tailored explicitly to emergency room procedures and acquired proficiency in responding to emergencies and managing disaster situations. According to Team (2024), the most important hard skills for emergency room nurses include essential life support (BLS), advanced cardiac life support (ACLS), triage, and critical care. The ability to multitask is necessary for ER nurses, who often must juggle multiple patients at once, and it can be a challenge, as each patient may have different needs and require different levels of care. Effectively multitasking ensures that all patients receive prompt and necessary care.

Table 12 reveals the test results for differences in nurses' knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response across monthly family income.

Table 12
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes in Emergency and Disaster Response Among Nurses Across Monthly Family Income

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Knowledge	Between Groups	.415	2	.208	1.494	.235	Not Significant
	Within Groups	6.531	47	.139			
	Total	6.946	49				
Skills	Between Groups	.821	2	.410	1.962	.152	Not Significant
	Within Groups	9.833	47	.209			
	Total	10.654	49				
Attitudes	Between Groups	.114	2	.057	.371	.692	Not Significant
	Within Groups	7.220	47	.154			
	Total	7.334	49				

The computed F-values, knowledge, skills, and attitudes have provided significance values higher than the set .05 significance level. It implies that the emergency and disaster response of the nurse in these aspects is the same when grouped according

to monthly family income. It revealed that regardless of the compensation received by the respondents, their knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response. Magsambol (2020) cited that Filipino nurses had been leaving the country for many years after failed attempts to fight for higher wages and better working conditions. Registered nurses hired by hospitals commonly receive an average salary of P9,757 a month. The government's average monthly wage is around P13,500; in the private sector, the average rate is around P10,000.

Table 13 presents the difference in nurses' knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response across several years in service. Aside from that, ER nurses also work long hours, often in high-stress situations, which can affect their well-being. Despite these challenges, ER nurses attend to their duties daily, providing the best possible care to their patients and ensuring that those in the most critical condition receive the needed attention.

Table 13
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes in Emergency and Disaster Response Among Nurses Across Number of Years in Service

Aspect	Source Variation	of	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Knowledge	Between Groups		.221	3	.074	.503	.682	Not Significant
	Within Groups		6.725	46	.146			
	Total		6.946	49				
Skills	Between Groups		1.189	3	.396	1.927	.138	Not Significant
	Within Groups		9.464	46	.206			
	Total		10.654	49				
Attitudes	Between Groups		.645	3	.215	1.479	.233	Not Significant
	Within Groups		6.689	46	.145			
	Total		7.334	49				

The statistical data indicate no significant difference in nurses' knowledge, skills, and attitude in emergency and disaster response regarding length of service. Nurses who are old and new in the service have comparable knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response. Before a nurse is assigned to the emergency room, she must have the competencies required in emergency and disaster response. Emergency and disaster care training is essential before a nurse is assigned to the ER. The study by McNeill et al. 2020 on nurses' preparedness during disasters indicates significant areas for improvement in nurses' professional emergency preparedness competence. While length of service may not significantly impact nurses' readiness in emergency and disaster response, ongoing efforts are needed to enhance nurses' preparedness and competence in this critical aspect of healthcare delivery. It includes

comprehensive training programs, regular drills, and the implementation of evidence-based practices to improve emergency response capabilities among nursing professionals.

Table 14 displays the results of the difference in nurses' knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response across a number of relevant trainings on emergency and disaster for the past five years.

The computed values suggest insignificant results, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. The amount of relevant training the nurses attend is consistent with their knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response. It implies that the respondents' relevant training did not cause any variation in their knowledge, skills, and attitudes regarding emergency and disaster response. Evidence shows that improved training strengthens disaster preparedness, enhancing the psychological preparedness of nurses during disasters; innovative learning and training strategies, such as high-fidelity modeling, are required to help educate nurses for disasters (Al Thobaity et al., 2017; Horrocks et al., 2019; Said & Chiang, 2020). Other studies have also reported low levels of disaster preparedness (Ahn et al., 2017; Labrague et al., 2018; Uhm et al., 2016). Labrague et al. (2016) reported that 80% of Filipino nurses suggested needing more time to bed to respond to disasters and highlighted the ongoing need for enhanced disaster preparedness training among nurses to ensure they are adequately equipped to respond effectively to emergencies and disasters. While the amount of relevant training attended may not significantly impact nurses' knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response, continual efforts are required to improve disaster preparedness training and ensure nurses are well-prepared to handle emergencies and disasters in healthcare settings.

Part IV: Pearson-r Correlation Stating the Results on the Significant Relationship Between the Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude Across their Profile Variables

Table 15 presents the relationship between nurses' knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response and their profile variables. Only knowledge in emergency and disaster response and a number of relevant trainings have shown a significant relationship with each other.

The significant positive R-value of .294 indicates a direct relationship. The more relevant training the nurses have attended, the more knowledgeable they are about emergency and disaster response. There are no significant relationships between knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response and the other profile variables, which implies that they do not vary.

Table 15
Relationship Between the Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes in Emergency and Disaster Response Among Nurses and their Profile Variables

Profile Variable	Knowledge		Skills		Attitude	
	r-value	sig	r-value	sig	r-value	sig
Age	.256	.073	.146	.313	.268	.060
Civil Status	.145	.315	.278	.051	.057	.694
Highest Educational Attainment	.115	.425	-.101	.486	.070	.629
Position	-.034	.812	-.167	.246	-.223	.119
Monthly Family Income	-.094	.516	-.253	.076	-.059	.682
Number of Years in Service	.003	.985	-.025	.862	-.047	.745
Number of Relevant Trainings on Emergency and Disaster	.294*	.039	.245	.086	.163	.258

***Significant at .05 level**

As cited by Al Thobaity et al. (2017), training is essential to strengthen disaster preparedness, enhancing psychological preparedness among nurses during disasters. Also, according to Balut et al. 2022, training healthcare workers in disaster preparedness has increased their willingness and ability to report to work during emergencies. These findings underscore the importance of ongoing training initiatives to improve disaster preparedness among healthcare workers, including nurses. By providing comprehensive training programs, healthcare institutions can ensure that their staff are well-prepared to respond to emergencies and disasters effectively, ultimately improving patient outcomes and overall healthcare resilience

Proposed Training Program for Emergency Room Nurses in Emergency and Disaster

General Objectives: To further enhance Emergency Room Nurses' knowledge, skills, and attitudes in response to emergency and disaster cases in the Emergency Room.

ASPECT: KNOWLEDGE	
Type of Training	
Advanced Emergency and Disaster Response Training	Capacity Building and Planning for the Unexpected Events Training
Title of Training Program	
“Quantum Care ER Tech: Empowering ER Nurses for High-Tech Emergency and Disaster Response”	“ER Dynamo: Energizing and Powering Emergency Room Nurses for the Unforeseen Challenges”
Objectives	
<p>To familiarize Emergency Room Nurses with the use of high-technology equipment.</p> <p>To enhance their proficiency in emergency and disaster response.</p>	<p>To Provide training to Emergency Room Nurses on effective triage and prioritization strategies, enabling them to assist patients with life-threatening and trauma cases promptly and efficiently.</p> <p>To familiarize Emergency Room Nurses with advanced medical equipment used in emergency and disaster response.</p>
Schedule	
<p>Once a year</p> <p>Every January</p>	<p>Once a year</p> <p>Every April</p>

Expected Output	
Emergency Room Nurses will demonstrate increased proficiency in operating high-tech equipment during emergencies and disasters.	Emergency Room Nurses will demonstrate efficient and accurate triage, ensuring critical patients receive timely care.

Improved patient care outcomes through the efficient use of advanced technology.	Emergency Room Nurses will confidently operate high-tech devices, optimizing patient care and outcomes.

ASPECT: SKILLS	
Type of Training	
Training on Hospital Referral System	Reorientation on the scope of responsibilities and policies of the Nursing Service
Title of Training Program	
“Referral Roadmap: Gabay para sa mga Nars sa ER”	“The Nursing Service Voyage: Pagbabalik-tanaw sa Ating mga Responsibilidad at Patakaran”
Objectives	
To understand the fundamentals and importance of an efficient hospital referral system, including its purpose, components, and workflow.	To review Emergency Room Nurses' responsibilities and update existing policies to ensure alignment with best practices and regulatory standards. To encourage continuous professional development among Emergency Room Nurses, fostering a culture of lifelong learning.
Schedule	
Once a year Every June	Once a year Every August
Expected Output	
Enhanced participants' grasp of hospital referral systems' purpose, components, and workflow.	Emergency Room Nurses will be more likely to comply with hospital rules and regulations, which will improve patient care, safety, and the prevention of errors in the Emergency Room.

Increased awareness of the importance of effective hospital referral processes in optimizing patient care and outcomes.	
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ASPECT: ATTITUDE	
Type of Training	
The Department of Health (DOH) - Attendance-based training	Stress Management seminar for nurses.
Title of Training Program	
Based on the Department of Health (DOH)-sponsored training program.	“Thriving In Turbulence: Emergency Nurses Stress Solutions
Objectives	
To foster awareness among healthcare professionals regarding the latest updates and trends in the healthcare system.	To prepare Emergency Room Nurses with effective stress reduction techniques. To minimize challenges encountered in the Emergency Room.
Schedule	
The training sessions will be scheduled according to the Department of Health (DOH) calendar. Participants will receive notifications regarding the dates and times of each session.	Once a year Every October
Expected Output	
Participants will have a deeper understanding of recent developments in healthcare policies, protocols, and best practices. They will be better equipped to adapt to changes, implement evidence-based approaches, and provide high-quality care to patients. Participants will gain insights into emerging trends that can positively impact their professional practice.	To prepare Emergency Room Nurses with effective stress reduction techniques and minimize challenges encountered in the Emergency Room.

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The nexus of knowledge, skills, and attitudes plays an essential role in emergency and disaster response among nurses. Therefore, efforts should be made to strengthen this nexus through continuous training, simulation exercises, a supportive work environment, personal development, and effective policymaking.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, the following are now concluded.

The nurse respondents were young adults, singles, and holders of bachelor's degrees; most were staff nurses earning an average monthly income, having been in the service for long years, and having inadequate relevant training in emergency and disaster nursing.

The respondents were knowledgeable about emergency and disaster response and skilled in attending to patients in the ER setting. They have adopted and practiced the appropriate attitudes necessary for managing emergency and disaster responses, recognizing the crucial importance of this skill. Moreover, their appropriate attitudes toward high-pressure situations are essential for effective and compassionate care.

These findings underscore the importance of continuous training and education to maintain high standards of emergency nursing care. It also points to the potential need for further development in certain areas, such as disaster preparedness training, to ensure that nurses are fully equipped to handle various emergency scenarios.

Nurses who finished units leading to a master's degree claim to have better skills in emergency and disaster response than those who are already master's degree holders. The skills of the nurses in emergency and disaster response are significantly different across positions. Staff nurses are more skilled and typically more involved in direct patient care and may, therefore, have more opportunities to apply and hone their emergency response skills than nurse supervisors.

Based on the findings, a comprehensive training program for emergency room (ER) nurses could be developed to enhance and improve their knowledge, skills, and attitudes in emergency and disaster response. This program would include focused education on emergency management principles, practical workshops for skills development such as triage assessment and rapid decision-making, simulated emergency scenarios to apply learned techniques in realistic settings, communication training to ensure effective coordination during crises, psychological support sessions to manage stress and trauma, discussions on ethical considerations in emergency care, continuous educational opportunities to remain informed about current best practices, and regular evaluations to assess program effectiveness and gather feedback for

improvement.

The more relevant training the nurses have attended, the more knowledgeable they are in emergency and disaster response.

The proposed training program is prepared to enhance further ER nurses' knowledge, skills, and attitudes.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions formulated, the following are now recommended:

The ER nurses must pursue more emergency and disaster response training, enhancing their preparedness and capabilities. Therefore, investing in additional training specific to emergency and disaster response is crucial for ensuring that nurses are well-prepared to handle various critical scenarios in the emergency room. Pursuing a graduate program in nursing can provide a deeper theoretical understanding and advanced practical skills, which are invaluable in emergencies.

Additionally, these programs provide nurses with opportunities to specialize in emergency and critical care, thereby arming them with specialized knowledge and expertise essential for navigating the distinctive challenges found in emergency room environments. Enhancing their experiences in handling emergency and disaster cases will further solidify their competencies and confidence in providing critical care. Furthermore, gaining more experience handling emergency and disaster cases is invaluable for emergency room nurses. Practical experience enables nurses to apply theoretical knowledge in real-life situations, fostering the development of critical thinking skills and bolstering confidence in their capacity to deliver exceptional care, even amidst high-pressure circumstances.

They must enhance their knowledge, skills, and attitudes by continuously updating themselves on new care trends for emergency and disaster patients. Continuous updating on new care trends for emergencies and disasters is essential for emergency room nurses to maintain competence, adaptability, and excellence in their practice. It ensures that nurses have the necessary skills and resources to meet patients' changing demands and provide excellent care during emergencies.

Nurses on the supervisory level must update themselves on emergency and disaster response. Supervisors should be on par with their staff nurses. This alignment in skills and knowledge between supervisors and staff nurses is essential for a cohesive and responsive team, especially in high-stress situations like emergencies and disasters. Furthermore, aligning supervisors' skills and knowledge with staff nurses fosters mutual respect, collaboration, and trust within the nursing team. It promotes a culture of teamwork and shared responsibility, where every member feels appreciated and empowered to contribute to the team's success. By aligning their skills and knowledge

with those of staff nurses, supervisors contribute to a culture of preparedness, collaboration, and excellence in emergency care delivery.

Conduct a hospital training program by inviting experts in emergencies and disasters. Inviting experts in the field of emergencies and disasters is an excellent initiative. Such training programs can significantly enhance the skills and knowledge of emergency room nurses, leading to improved patient care outcomes and potentially saving more lives during critical situations.

Hospitals can adapt training programs to improve patient care outcomes, save more lives, and enhance the skills of emergency room nurses. By staying current with the latest practices and technologies in emergency care, emergency room nurses can be better prepared to face the challenges of their demanding roles.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured that ethical precautions and procedures were followed throughout the study. In the whole process of this study, the researcher considered ethical precautions to follow:

Informed Consent: Before initiating the study, the researcher ensured that all participants provided informed consent. This included providing detailed information about the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, potential risks and benefits, confidentiality measures, and the voluntary nature of participation.

Confidentiality: The researcher implemented measures to safeguard the confidentiality of participants' information. These measures included anonymizing data, assigning participant codes, securely storing data, and controlling access to identifiable information. By doing so, the privacy of participants was preserved throughout the study.

Voluntary Participation: Participants were assured that their participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and they maintained the right to withdraw at any juncture without encountering any negative repercussions. Notably, there was a commitment to refrain from coercion or pressure to participate.

Avoidance of Harm: The researcher took steps to minimize the risk of harm to participants, both physical and psychological. This includes conducting the study to respect participants' dignity, privacy, and emotional well-being.

Disclosure of Conflicts of Interest: The researcher disclosed any potential conflicts of interest that could affect the integrity or impartiality of the study.

Transparency: The researcher provided clear and transparent communication about the study's purpose, methods, findings, and implications, both to participants and to the broader research community

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